

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF COMPOUND WORDS IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT: In this given article the author analyzed the linguistic features and new formation and creation of the compound words in English and in Uzbek. Also, he tried to learn that Word formation is the creation of new lexical units based on the material and possibilities available in the language. This process serves to enrich the content of the language dictionary on a regular basis. One of the most commonly used word forms today, which is considered to be holistic and concise, as well as productive, is compound words. Compound words are a very important and relevant phenomenon for all languages. The author affirms that most of the new words and compound words that come into our language are in English. For example, a cell phone, a cheeseburger, a playboy, and so on. The English word-formation system has its own linguistic features, and the study of the phenomenon of word-formation in terms of synchronous and diachronic periods of language development has always been a topical issue. Including compound words in English requires special attention.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье автор проанализировал лингвистические особенности и новообразования сложных слов в английском и узбекском языках. Кроме того, он попытался понять, что словообразование - это создание новых лексических единиц на основе материала и возможностей, имеющих в языке. Этот процесс служит для регулярного пополнения словаря. Сегодня одной из наиболее часто используемых словоформ, которая считается целостной и лаконичной, а также продуктивной, являются сложные слова. Сложные слова - очень важное и актуальное явление для всех языков. Автор утверждает, что

большинство новых слов и сложных словосочетаний, которые входят в наш язык, заимствованы из английского языка. Например, сотовый телефон, чизбургер, плейбой и так далее. Английская словообразовательная система имеет свои лингвистические особенности, и изучение феномена словообразования с точки зрения синхронного и диахронического периодов развития языка всегда было актуальной проблемой.

ABSTRACT: Ushbu maqolada muallif ingliz va o'zbek tillarida qo'shma so'zlarning til xususiyatlari va yangi shakllanishi va yaratilishini tahlil qildi. Shuningdek, u so'z shakllanishi tilda mavjud bo'lgan material va imkoniyatlar asosida yangi leksik birliklarni yaratish ekanligini o'rganishga harakat qildi. Ushbu jarayon til lug'atining mazmunini muntazam ravishda boyitishga xizmat qiladi. Bugungi kunda yaxlit va ixcham, shuningdek samarali deb hisoblanadigan eng ko'p ishlatiladigan so'z shakllaridan biri bu qo'shma so'zlardir. Murakkab so'zlar barcha tillar uchun juda muhim va dolzarb hodisadir. Muallif bizning tilimizga kiradigan yangi so'zlar va qo'shma so'zlarning aksariyati ingliz tilida ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Masalan, uyali telefon, cheeseburger, playboy va boshqalar. Inglizcha so'z hosil qilish tizimi o'ziga xos lingvistik xususiyatlarga ega va so'z shakllanishi hodisasini til rivojlanishining sinxron va diaxronik davrlari nuqtai nazaridan o'rganish har doim dolzarb bo'lib kelgan.

Keywords: compound words, linguistic features, lexical units, word formation, and phenomenon

Introduction. A language is a tool of communication, both in written and spoken form, used to deliver ideas and feelings from one person to another. It is used to refer to our husband, wife, friends, teachers, rivals, or even enemies. The use of language in our daily activities can show the language user's emotions and feelings and construct a society. Generally, learning a language is built from small parts into a big unit. It means that language has been the largest unit of the sentence. It consists of clauses, phrases, words, and even letters. The population of humans is significantly increasing and developing. Therefore, language as a tool of

communication changes rapidly.

In the morphological process, there are many ways to create words, such as inflection, derivation, and compounding. Inflection is the morphological process of a lexeme, creating many forms for that lexeme. It is called a "set of grammatical words." Furthermore, derivation is the way of forming a new word from an existing word. It can be created by adding a prefix or suffix. On the other hand, compounding or composition consists of the combination of two words into new lexemes. It can often be challenging to tell whether a statement is made up of a phrase or a compound when trying to grasp it. Due to their similarities in some ways, it may be difficult to tell if it is a compound or a noun. For instance, the meaning of greenhouse and greenhouse is similar, leading us to believe there is no difference between the two. However, by returning to the theories, it will be possible to overcome the challenge of identifying a phrase from a compound. This study consists primarily of a morphological analysis to determine the type of compounding that was utilized in the life and style column in the Jakarta Globe. The part of speech used by the compound and its constituents allows us to morphologically identify the use of the compound in the text. Additionally, this study concentrates on the semantic connections between the compound and its head in terms of the semantic aspect. Compound Words Compounds are words created by combining roots with the considerably smaller category of phrasal words, that is, objects that have the internal structure of phrasal but function syntactically as words Carstairs (2002:59). Furthermore, Katamba (1993:291) adds that A compound word is defined as a term made up of at least two bases that can arise elsewhere as independent words. 3. Some Work on the Analysis of Compound Words We have two tasks in the analysis of a compound word: identification of its constituents and then the determination of its structure. Our present interest lies in the latter task. There are numerous studies on the identification for the constituents of a compound word. To mention a few, Miyazaki et al. (1984) used a handcrafted, rule-based method and a technique of

ambiguity resolution for segmenting a compound word. Takeda and Fujisaki (1987) segmented kanji compound words using Markov Model. Utiyama and Itahashi (1992) divided a compound noun expressed in hiragana characters into component nouns based on word cooccurrence relation. In recent ones, Shimohata et al. (1997) and Fujii et al. (1999) segmented a compound word into its constituents employing simple heuristics based mainly on the features of Japanese character types. Han et al. (2001a) devised a segmentation strategy using contextual information from a corpus. Relatively few studies are available on the determination of dependency structure of a compound word. Nishino and Fujisaki (1988) attempted to analyze the structure of a kanji compound word using a probabilistic CFG. Miyazaki et al. (1993) used a large amount of handcrafted rules and resolved the ambiguities on semantic structure in compound words. These studies are all rule-based and have obvious deficiencies. Obtaining rules is time-consuming process to begin with. Then rules are limited, fixed and not easily extendable. Recently the researchers have turned to corpus and statistical means to analyzing the structure of compound words. Along this line, Kobayasi et al. (1994) built dependency trees for a compound word, calculated the likelihood of each tree structure using collocational information on its constituents extracted from a corpus, and selected the one with the highest likelihood value as the correct structure of the compound word. In this process, they used a thesaurus and got the collocational data through its classes to which each constituent of a compound word belongs. Using a similar method, Hisamitsu and Nitta (1996), in an analysis of compound words extracted from news articles,, tried to overcome a deficiency in the study of Kobayasi et al. that it could not deal with abbreviated words or, for that matter, unknown words in the corpus used. However, the method he adapted seems restricted only to the analysis of newspaper articles. Our method of analyzing the structure of a compound word is corpus- and statistics- based, too. But it is different from others in a few points. Methodologically, it uses a deterministic process. Computationally, we calculate the strength of association,

for the constituent words in a compound word using mutual information-like measures and determine its correct structure by discarding less probable ones along the way. Data-wise, we use the Internet corpus to coping with data sparseness problem and getting reliable statistical information. Structural Analysis of Compound Word Our idea for analyzing the structure of compound words is similar to those used in various disambiguation tasks (e.g., Alves, 1996; Wu & Furugori, 1996; Karov et a u & Furugori, 1996; Karov et al., 1998). We all use a kind of corpora and statistical means and then eliminate the more unlikely and select the more likely to get the desired result. However, the difference is that we use a deterministic process and keep discarding less likely candidates along the way we go, rather than collecting all the candidates first and then selecting the most probable one from them. The definition of "compound word" is defined in the modern literature as follows: "Words formed by the combination of two or more stems are called compound words." Composition (the phenomenon of compound word formation), the resulting compound words have been interpreted differently by linguists over the years, and the general theoretical foundations between them are shared. A.I. Smirnitsky (1956) considers compound words as a single unit of form and describes them as a linguistic unit that cannot be divided into parts, no element can be added between its components, and the position cannot be changed. A similar definition is given in O.S. Akhmanova's "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms". Views on the form integrity of compound words are also stated by O.D. Meshkov (1985). The compound word as R.B.Liz (1960) and H.Marchand (1965) derives from the following syntactic structure and represents one of eight types of grammatical connections (Liz, 1960, pp. 125-168):

Vocabulary → compound word: eight grammatical connections:

- a. Subject-Predicate: "the plane is a fighter" → fighter plane
- b. Subject-Middle Object: "the bone has marrow" → marrow bone
- c. Subject-Verb: "the bird wades" → wading bird
- d. Subject-Object: "dog which is the police use" or "dog which serves the

police” → police dog

f. Verb-Object: “(John) pushes the button” → pushbutton

g. Subject-Prepositional Object: “the cream is for coffee” → coffee cream

c. Verb-Prepositional Object: “(John) grinds knives on the stone” → grindstone

d. Object-Prepositional Object: “we teach the grammar in school” → school grammar

H. Marchand (1965) believes that compound words are formed on the basis of syntactic formation by combining linguistic units on the basis of the determinative+ definite relation. In his view, the morphological combination of two or more words can be called a compound word. W. Adams (1973) defines a compound word as the result of a combination of two free forms or words that exist independently. For example, frostbite, tape-measure, grass-green. Although these elements consist of two elements, they have the defining properties of a single word: their components are inseparable from other words, and their order is strict. According to P.H. Matthews (1974: 82), the formation of a compound word is the formation of a compound lexeme from two or more simple lexemes. S. Ulman (1972: 81) says that each compound word contains words that are free and vague in meaning and have no connection in terms of sound and meaning, while others consist of words that are at least somewhat motivated or understandable. R.S. Ginzburg et al. (1979) consider compound word formation or composition to be one of the most effective forms of word formation in modern English. As with all other methods of word formation, analyzing the specific features of the composition, such as the means used, the nature and distribution of the bases, the scope, the scope of semantic classes, and the factors that increase productivity, “compound words consist of two direct components. Compound words are integral word units. They depend on the foundations that reflect the relationship between the formal and semantic substantiation units and the semantic relationship between them.” L. Bauer (1983) shows two features of compound words in

English:

1) the majority of compound words in English are made according to the N+N model; 2) there are different semantic and syntactic relations between the components of the compound word and study them in 4 structurally-functional groups. The first group includes endocentric joint nouns. The second component of such compound word components is grammatically and semantically superior, while the first component serves as a determiner. For example: beehive, armchair. The second group includes exocentric compound nouns (or uses the Sanskrit term “bahuvrihi” for them). In such compound nouns the grammatical and semantic superiority is not clearly expressed, in which the components acquire a metaphorical or metonymic character. For example: skinheads. In the third group, the components of the compound word are treated in the same way as the sentence(s). For example: maidservant. In the fourth group, the scientist enters compound words that it is not clear which component is grammatically or semantically dominant. Such compound nouns are referred to as "dvandva" in the compound compound word or Sanskrit term. For example: poettranslator. O.D. Meshkov (1985) describes compound words in English as follows: it is formed by the union of two or more bases, and it manifests itself in speech as an indivisible lexical unit”. He divides compound words into the following two groups according to the sign of motivation:

1) Structurally motivated compound words - derive from the sum of the meanings of the components of the common meaning.

2) Structurally unmotivated compound words - do not arise from the sum of the meanings of the components of the common meaning. According to I.V. Arnold (1986), “Compound words are words consisting of at least two bases that occur in language as free forms. The fact that the direct components of a compound word have integrity and structural unity ensures that they serve as a separate lexical unit in the sentence. He considers the problem of defining this type of word to be the connection, transparency, or idiomatic meanings between

the components. Along with the naming of the types of compound words given in the "English Lexicology," he distinguishes them into asyntactic and syntactic, endocentric, and exocentric types. I.V. Arnold (1986) cites in describing the different criteria of compound words Yu. Nide, L. Blumfield, G. Paul, R. Querk, B. Blok, D. Trager, G. Marchand, A.I. Smirnitsky's views and uses them effectively. As S. Greenbaum (1996: 461) points out, a compound word (addition or composition) is one of the four basic methods of word formation in modern English - prefixation, suffixation, and conversion, formed by combining two or more bases. When we say reason, S. Greenbaum (1996) understands the word motivating (doubt for doubt, doubted for doubt, undoubtedly for doubt). The researcher says that compound words occur in all word categories, but among newcomers, nouns and adjectives predominate. Some compound nouns have a repetitive feature - both parts are the same or cause the two parts to be slightly different: clever-clever, teeny-weeny. Newly formed words in English are mainly words belonging to the adjective and noun phrases. Historically, compound words have come mainly from noun phrases. They can be passed on in the conversion method, through the transfer of meaning from one word group to another. For example, blackmail, cold-shoulder, daydream. Or through back-formation, i.e. the method of dropping suffixes in a word. For example, babysitting (from babysitting or babysitter), double-park (from double parking), shoplift (from shoplifting). The most common type among compound nouns, i.e. the second (or last) component, refers to the class of the word: travel guide is the type of travel guide, pop group is the type of group. Other joint nouns do not have such a ratio, or at least may be hidden: a white lady is not a face, a hotdog does not mean a dog. S. Greenbaum (1996) believes that the relationship between the components of a compound word can be described using grammatical terminology. Indicates that the following typical models of compound words are formed: Subject + predicate: bee sting ('bee stings') Predicate + subject: answerphone ('phone answers') Predicate + object: chewing gum ('chews gum') Object + predicate: air-conditioner ('conditions

air') Subject + object: cable car ('the cable operates the car') Object + subject: honeybee ('bee produces honey') Predicate + tool: hearing aid ('hears with aid') Tool + predicate: gunfight ('fights with a gun') Predicate + place: dance hall ('dances in a hall') Place + predicate: boat ride ('rides on boat') Predicate + time: closing time ('closes at that time') Time + predicate: daydreaming ('dreams during day'). In some compound nouns consisting of two nouns or adjectives and nouns, the "subject + predicate" relation can be expressed using the verb to be connected: adjective + noun: passive smoking (the smoking is passive ') Noun + noun 'A from B': booster shot ('the shot is a booster') 'B like A': magnet school (the school is like a magnet ') 'A for B': ashtray ('the tray is for ash') 'B part of A' :door handle ('the handle of a door'). A type of compound noun, which is the first component of a noun or adjective, depends entirely on the compound word: loudmouth ('person who has a loud mouth') paperback ('book that has a paper cover'). S. Greenbaum (1996) describes the semantic connection between the components of compound adjectives as follows: subject + predicate: English-speaking ('speaks English') place/time/reason + predicate: far-reaching ('reaches far') Noun + adjective 'A is B': footsore ('the foot is sore') 'A as B': dirt-cheap ('as cheap as dirt') 'A comes from B': camera-shy ('shy in respect of cameras') 'A and B': bitter-sweet In his book of lexicology, G.B. Antrushina et al (1999: 104-113) give three different views, each of which is divided into different types of composition, which is noteworthy. In the history of Uzbek linguistics, language phenomena have been interpreted mainly on the basis of the ideas of other languages, including the doctrines of Russian linguistics, on the principles of ready-made word forms. Under the influence of Russian linguistics and related literature, word formation in Uzbek linguistics has also been separated from morphology. However, it was only taking into account the fact that forming words is a different phenomenon in comparison with word formation. Each of them, including word formation, did not work on the basis that they formed a separate system, and it was natural. Because in Uzbek linguistics, even the basic concepts of word formation, their essence,

process of word formation and related events were not covered properly. For over the last years the Uzbek language has developed comprehensively and in all its spheres significant changes have occurred in accordance with the requirements of the time. The demand for covering changes in this process has always been in the development of Uzbek linguistics. Scientific and theoretical work on all areas of Uzbek linguistics has been done, especially the development of the Uzbek language during this period and the coverage of the special laws on language that have been in force in progress. Particular attention was paid to the development of the national language after gaining independence, and some measures were taken to achieve it.

Conclusion: Based on the findings and discussion above, it can be concluded that there were several types of compound words that occur in the article entitled “Designers of the Runaway as Jakarta Fashion Weeks Takes off” from the life and style column in Jakarta Globe. They were seven types of compound nouns and one compound verb. Those compounds nouns were chairwoman, chief executive, fashion week, showroom, trade event, vivacity, and rainbow. Compound nouns is the commonest type of compound in English. In this stage, the position of the main stress is in the right-headed. Further, the word highlighted was found in the text as a compound verb. The example above is Furthermore, from seven compound nouns, there were two words identified as an exocentric compound that a compound named a subtype. The type is not represented by the head or the modifier in the compound. Those kind of words were not head. They were vivacity and rainbow. On the other hand, the compound words of chairwoman, chief executive, fashion week, showroom, trade event, and highlighted were classified as endocentric compounds which represent head where the endocentric compound consists of subtypes of whatever the head represents.

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